

Giovanni Boldini and Haute Couture: from Christian Dior to John Galliano

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Abstract: The essay illustrates the birth of haute couture in Paris and the role played by Giovanni Boldini as a link between the worlds of fashion and art. In his works, Boldini depicts the ladies of the high Parisian aristocracy offering aesthetic legitimacy to the nascent world of fashion, and exerting a profound influence on Christian Dior, who in his memoirs recalls Boldini as his primary source of inspiration. The dreamy image of the golden world of Parisian haute société immortalized by Boldini also has a profound influence on John Galliano, whose direct quotes of Boldini's artistic production are highlighted here, honing in on the accessories.

Keywords: Giovanni Boldini, Christian Dior, haute couture, painting, fashion.

Resumen: El ensayo ilustra el nacimiento de la alta costura en París a finales del siglo XIX y el papel desempeñado por el pintor Giovanni Boldini como un vínculo entre el mundo de la moda y el del arte. En sus obras, Boldini retrata a las damas de la alta aristocracia parisina pintadas con los vestidos de los más importantes modistos de la época, ofreciendo legitimidad estética al naciente mundo de la moda, y ejerciendo una profunda influencia en Christian Dior, quien

en sus memorias recuerda a Boldini como su principal fuente de inspiración. La imagen del mundo dorado de la alta sociedad parisina, inmortalizada por Boldini a partir de 1890 en sus retratos femeninos, también tiene una profunda influencia en John Galliano, de quien destacamos las citas directas de la producción artística de Boldini en dos de sus importantes desfiles de moda realizados en la Ópera Garnier y en el Castillo de Versalles. De esta manera, ilustramos el papel central desempeñado por Boldini en la inspiración de las creaciones de Dior y del más talentoso estilista que ha trabajado para la famosa Maison, centrando la atención en los accesorios.

Palabras clave: Giovanni Boldini, Christian Dior, alta costura, pintura, moda.

The Belle Époque made a strong come-back recently in two fashion shows by Maison Dior planned by John Galliano: the 1998 Spring/Summer collection at the Opera Garnier, and the 2007-08 Autumn/Winter collection at the Orangerie in Versailles. Both go down in the history of fashion as a new way of drawing on the legacy of an illustrious past to update the same, bringing the spirit and seductiveness of French *fin-de-siècle* style into the present, as a precious source of inspiration from the period in which modern fashion was born. When we speak about the Belle Époque era, the name of the Italian painter Giovanni Boldini (1842–1931) immediately comes to mind, together with those of his closest friends, the painter Georges Helleu, the draughtsman Georges Gourçat, known as Sem, and the count Robert de Montesquiou-Fézensac. The latter was used as a model by Joris-Karl Huysmans for his famous novel *À rebours* (1884), the so-called 'bible' of the Decadents, and was therefore called 'the king of transient things' by his contemporaries. The name Boldini would have been very familiar to a certain young and talented designer born in 1905, because the painter died in Paris in 1931, when Christian Dior was already 26 years old. Thus, in the years he attended the École des Sciences Politiques and throughout 1928 when he opened his art gallery, Dior, as a young and talented aspiring designer certainly had in mind, the mind of Boldini, his paintings of sinuous models, sensual and alluring, dressed in the most sumptuous clothes created by Parisian designers.

Christian Dior's love for Boldini dates back to his cultural education. Dior recognized that he owed part of his aesthetic to the Italian painter, who in

1890 became the official portraitist of the Parisian high society noblewomen. However, it was also indebted to the fact that high fashion in *fin-de-siècle* Paris, that is, at the moment of its first affirmation, created forms and shapes destined to last forever, remaining a constant in the development of all subsequent haute couture. I am referring to traits such as seduction, charm, and a languid femininity, mixed with a complex and sophisticated psychology. In a word, fashion, conceived as a social distinction, is linked to a concept of high life that was taking shape in Paris at the end of the nineteenth century, fuelled by aristocratic snobbery, which leveraged the new bourgeoisie's anxiety for social ascent. The bourgeoisie, until then, had not been allowed to penetrate the golden and secluded world of the high aristocracy, encouraging the latter to make its privilege even more evident.

In fact, the aristocracy would become at that precise moment – that is to say, at the end of the nineteenth century – a group resented by the middle classes who were advancing in the fields of politics and economics, while previously it had simply been at the top of the social pyramid, immovable, unattainable and impervious to external influences. Before the birth of the large European industrial communities in the nineteenth century, which arose in conjunction with the urban development

of the great metropolises of London and Paris, the concentration of wealth was exclusively located within the aristocratic estates. But from the first decades of the nineteenth century onwards, banking and financial elites arose from the nascent bourgeoisie, which placed themselves at the top of the civil consortium in terms of wealth and political influence. However, for these new social powers, the most important stratum, that of high society and worldliness, remained unreachable. That was in fact an area that could not be conquered by skill and will alone, it had to be inherited. It was part of the privilege of birth, closely linked to the spheres of art, taste, culture and, eventually, fashion. The bourgeoisie tried to imitate aristocratic behaviour with such fury that the nobility decided to change its own habits so as not to be invaded by the presence of the middle class, as happened on the occasion of the première of Richard Wagner's *Lohengrin* in Rome:

“Since it is very good manners not to miss premières and since this aristocratic custom has for some time been imitated, as always, by the bourgeoisie, I believe that, precisely out of horror of this imitation, the ladies of the nobility will gradually withdraw from the use and will leave free field to the bourgeois beauties in the first

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performances. Thus, the premières will become a vulgarity, and the most chic evenings will perhaps be those of the second premières. Last night in fact the bourgeoisie dominated, but many illustrious ladies of the nobility were missing: and they were missing (I know from Donna Claribel) on purpose" (D'Annunzio, [1884] 1948: 12).

Aristocracy, as a hegemonic and preeminent class that had slowly begun to welcome selected exponents of the bourgeoisie – who made capital flow into the increasingly empty coffers of the nobility –, would see fashion as an instrument to impose a new form of influence, using taste and style as a way to restore their prestige when their economic means were dwindling. Thus, fashion became even more elitist, because it derived from the impalpable regions of a new aesthetic: a form of fashion mixed with refined social rituals and an interdisciplinary and lively modern culture. At the end of the nineteenth century, fashion established itself as ‘the tenth Muse’ and a new art form. Haute couture, embodied in the creations of Charles Frederick Worth and Paul Poiret, was not yet a canonical form of ‘official culture’, and therefore also escaped the dominion of intellectuals, be they critics, artists, or writers. Fashion was born as an art conceived specifically for women and refined men of high society, to express their sense of inwardness and their outside passions, which in the latter case coincided, rather than with traditional male values, with the spirit of a new era, born in the name of a sophisticated and androgynous culture, dominated by Beauty.

Fashion can be conceived, in fact, as a peculiar expression of the *fin-de-siècle* Decadent taste, because its main goal is to give voice to the secret passions of the unconscious, through an exquisite, precious and refined style. Fashion, rejecting a realistic and positivistic perspective, embodies the mirage of a mystical and irrational dream, and does so through artificial forms modelled on their creator’s imagination. Such unconventional and voluptuous forms, by conveying the designer’s inner world, help us know the most profound and unattainable layer of reality, which is apparently invisible and is connected, through a secret network of relationships, to the soul of each of us, according to Baudelaire’s theory of *Correspondances*. The artist is simply capable of bringing out from itself this hidden stratum of the human psyche, common to all of us, rendering it visible. This is the reason we are so attracted to fashion, because, like the poetry of the Symbolists, like the colorful words of Arthur Rimbaud and the musicality of Paul Verlaine’s *Fêtes Galantes*, it expresses the magmatic and pulsating life of tormented and exceptional psychologies, which, by opening their suggestive and fascinating abyss, reveal

the essence of the most authentic reality that surrounds us, which connects itself to our unconscious. Fashion, so to speak, reveals us to ourselves and highlights our desires, even those of which we are not immediately aware. The dreamy forms and the refined style of fashion, overcoming the imitative way of reproducing the visible reality typical of nineteenth-century realism, illustrate the depths of our collective soul, by virtue of the visionary energy of the designers, who, just as Rimbaud hoped in his famous letter of 15th May 1871 to Paul Demeny, take on the role of authentic “seers”, digging into the depths of one’s soul and reaching that common ground of passions and desires that is the foundation of every human nature, triggering a bewitching mechanism of identification.

Every figure in Boldini’s portraits “gets thinner, oscillates, dislocates” for the sole purpose of increasing their sense of originality:

“... the zigzag of these busts, these elbows, these knees, in their sketched appearance, has something truly energetic and vital. Boldini paints the rough, capricious and restless side of modern temperaments” (Soulier, 1904: 201–09).

In this way, the ‘vestals’ of the ‘Tout Paris’ portrayed by Giovanni Boldini had a strong cultural hegemony, which would in turn have considerable social influence. We can say that high fashion, as we conceive it today, established itself in Paris at the end of the nineteenth century, as the nobility’s attempt to reaffirm its social prestige, which had declined after the French Revolution. That goal could not be achieved through money, but rather through something that the emerging bourgeoisie could not materially procure for itself: culture, taste, and style.

A new form of art was born, the only owners of which were the noble and fascinating women of the European aristocracy, and its charm and authority increased through Boldini’s dynamic and seductive paintings. The secret of this innovative style of painting is, in a word, movement. The painter’s brush captures every reflection of the materials from which dresses are made, even minimum nuances of colour. His models are represented while moving, as if talking to him. They are often provocative, surrounded by an aura of sensual and seductive charm, enhancing their natural beauty with soft and supple movements of a powerful erotic resonance. Many critics underlined negatively

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this aspect of Boldini's art, saying that it was animated by "a disturbing and perverse grace" (Tausserat-Radel, 2015: 19), and Octave Mirbeau noted that Boldini expressed

"... an annoying exaggeration, a desire for deplorable indiscretion [...] Boldini doesn't undress his models, he does much worse. He takes pleasure in provocatively exposing their bodies, ruffling the fabrics on their back, on the thighs or on the hollows [...]. The scandalous intent is undeniable and graceless" (Mirbeau, 1892: 484).

This new style of painting, like the new fashion, gave voice to the impulses of transgression dictated by the new poetics of the Decadent movement, as the famous writer Max Nordau underlines in 1907 when talking about Boldini's works:

"Every fibre of his women throbs and pulsates. One of these sits naked, [...] with only an expression of savage cruelty. There is an atmosphere of hysterical convulsion in these paintings, reminiscent of San Vito's Ball [...]. I can't believe that people pay 30,000 francs for one of these paintings: but if a woman is ready to shell out a cent to be depicted by Boldini as a Bacchante or a Vampire, then she must be a victim of neurosis exactly as he represents her" (Nordau, 1907: 225).

But this rarefied languor, ignited by sudden flashes of desire – which made the most conservative critics claim that this kind of painting was a sort of 'boudoir aesthetic' – is precisely what will characterize many aspects of fashion in the contemporary age, which, starting with Christian Dior, would impose itself as a dreaming world in which the most driven and secret desires could again take shape after the gloom of the World Wars, in a society newly animated by a renascent economy. This happened through the strategy of a calculated mechanism of emotional identification on the part of a public that saw in haute couture the resurgence of the Belle Époque. Those effects, active still today, took Parisians back to a moment of expression and fulfilment of their deepest and most unspeakable desires, based on a new conception of morality, now animated by the rejection of ordinary bourgeoisie values. Fashion is the world of dreams, and these are inextricably linked to sexuality, which has arisen, since the years of Freud's discoveries on the unconscious, as the nucleus of the most authentic and deep-rooted desires and aspirations of our personality, conscious and unconscious. This is why, in the same years in which Freud published his research, Boldini's paintings are so appreciated and fascinating in such a pervasive way: they embody the desire of women who would like to be uninhibited and transgressive like the models portrayed by the Ferrara painter; the appetites of men who would remain fascinated by their

attractiveness; and, finally, the dreams of men who would identify themselves with those seductive and beautiful women. The core of Decadentism, expressed in painting by Boldini and in literature by Baudelaire, Verlaine, and Huysmans, is all in the attempt to reach what is eccentric and aestheticizing through what is artificial, rare and extravagant, with the aim of replacing the positivistic values of the bourgeoisie with those of Beauty as an alternative to traditional moral codes. In the years immediately following the Second World War, this becomes the artistic objective of Dior's fashion, which recovers the cultural codes of late Romantic poetics, exalting the impulses of desire above ordinary social conventions.

While after World War II other forms of art move towards realism, and their aim becomes not to express the desire of a tormented psychology, but simply to represent the objective aspect of reality, fashion remains, thanks mainly to Dior, firmly anchored to the sensual, exuberant and aestheticizing universe of desire, dreams and imagination: this is the secret of its success and the message launched by Galliano's attempt to recover the brilliant and seductive atmosphere of Boldini's Belle Époque chronicles. What links Boldini's paintings to the fashion world is the sense of aristocratic privilege; his art is a direct reflection of social privilege. The search for originality carried out by the Decadents implies drawing on what is rare, precious, and therefore inscribed in an aura of privilege, searchable and obtainable only in elitist contexts, since society as it was structured in the nineteenth century, exclusively founded on the power of money and social distinctions, makes the latter the only means by which to take possession of what is authentically desirable. Only high society could freely express its personality, since the political consensus of late nineteenth-century Europe was based on the repression of the masses, on the limits imposed on the ways of life of the poorest. Therefore fashion, which was the embodiment par excellence of dream and desire, was a form of expression which could only be listed among the exclusive prerogatives of the hegemonic classes. Fashion, as Boldini showed in his works of art, and Dior and Galliano in their quotations from his so unique style, remained even in the twentieth and twenty-first centuries a form of art deeply linked to the example of the late Romanticism and Decadent taste. It expresses desire, so it corresponds to privilege and

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exclusivity, because even our present society is firmly structured upon social class distinctions and upon the possibility, reserved for the few, of embodying so-called 'desire'.

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Boldini's women are conceived as models of a sort of fashion show that takes place in painting instead of on a catwalk. To obtain this effect he produced a precise mixture of colour, to achieve a sense of density which would render the tactile thickness of fabrics. He studied contemporary fashion in depth, visiting the most famous ateliers, and becoming acquainted with the designers themselves. He established an important connection between the world of art and that of fashion, opening a precious and unexplored path for future generations of artists. We could say that he anticipated, in various ways, modernity's taste. Moreover, it's worth noting that Boldini often told his models to wear a specific dress, because he aimed to represent them wearing it, as in the case of Madame Doyen, who ordered a dress from Poiret for her portrait by Boldini in 1910, delaying the moment of going to the painter's studio until she had received her beloved *mise*.

The analysis of the aesthetic filiation of some of Maison Dior's creative seasons to *fin-de-siècle* taste is a research topic that finds justification in the fact that some specific aspects of modern and contemporary haute couture reflect the legacy of nineteenth- and early twentieth-century fashion, and of the pictorial transfiguration wrought by Giovanni Boldini. In his paintings, the clothes of the most fashionable Parisian couturiers are enhanced, as we already pointed out, through an unprecedented effect of movement, which, with ever-increasing dynamic intensity, would constitute one of the distinctive features of modernity. A modernity, however, integrated into a figurative discourse, comparable to that solid connection to the 'pompiers' style which has always constituted an irreplaceable mental reference of the establishment. In Boldini's portraits we find modernity and dynamism, but applied to the familiar forms of the female silhouette. Women sheathed in tight impalpable corsets and body-hugging fabrics would take shape in Christian Dior's adolescent memories, as he wrote in 1951 for *Je suis couturier*: "Of the women of my childhood what remains above all is the memory of the swirls of fur, Boldini-style gestures" (Dior, 1951: 49). And in a dress created by Dior for the Autumn/Winter 1955 collection,¹ we see both gestures and stylistic choices in

¹ <https://hprints.com/en/item/97652/Christian-Dior-Fur-Clothing-1955-Opaline-Royal-Canadian-Bijoux-Cartier-Photo-Virginia-Thoren>.

the clothing recognizable from a famous Boldinian painting (fig. 1) in which his model wears, over a red dress, a precious fur. We are reminded of the sensual value of fur as a garment that triggered the erotic imagination of the most attentive and refined observers:

“The Roman ladies are pale, mostly hidden by a dense veil, sunk in the softness of the furs. Oh, beautiful otter coats decorated with blond beavers! The very shiny fur opens here and there like an ear of corn, varying the same dark color with golden appearances. Nothing is more elegantly voluptuous than an otter fur that has already been used for some time. Then the animal skins allow all the flexibility of the female body; but not with the light adhesion of silk and satin; although with a certain gravity not without those sweet graces that animals with rich fur have in their movements furtive: always a kind of flash, a kind of sudden lucidity precedes or accompanies the movement, and gives the movement a strange beauty” (D’Annunzio, [1884] 1948: 1).

Many Dior creations from the early 1950s are homages to Belle Époque haute couture, idealized by Boldini in his full-length portraits of women depicted like ‘living lianas’, sensually animated by a secret and restless interior life, which, in making them exuberant and lively, reflected a psychological complexity nourished by aspirations and desires still too audacious to be accepted by the mentality of the time. Jean-Louis Vaudoyer writes that Boldini’s women are “large living flowers” (Vaudoyer, 1931: 1192), and they unfold like corollas as the “petals” of their dresses merge with those of their epidermis in a complicity between flesh and fabrics, as Robert de Montesquiou acutely noted. The same could be said of Dior’s creations, when starting from 1947 he renewed the New Look by creating precisely the image of the ‘flower woman’. The dress, so to speak, is like a chalice that encloses light layers of petals to envelop tender and fragile pistils, in a floral and ornamental interpretation of the female silhouette similar to that carried out by Boldini, who aimed to transform nature, in its ephemeral transience, in a complete and perfect entity. From this point of view, Boldini anticipated a central aim of modern fashion: escaping the ordinary life, its expiration and its sadness. In his portraits Boldini created a world made of dreams, he gave life to a cosmos of almost otherworldly beauties, just as the stylists of the twentieth and twenty-first centuries would. The ambitions of these designers are always centered on rebuilding a universe of unconventional desires, in an attempt to overcome

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Figure 1 | Giovanni Boldini, *Mme. Juillard in Red*, oil on canvas, 1912. Private collection.

the narrow limits set by the bourgeoisie and consumeristic codes. Boldini's artistic production was so voraciously sought after precisely because, as we already pointed out, it embodied the aspirations of a social class that desired to live, as the dandy Gabriele D'Annunzio would write in the same years, in an "inimitable" way, and to make Beauty its guide in life. Beauty would descend from heaven and abandon its divine guise to take on a human form, becoming tangible and concrete.

This happened both in Boldini's paintings and in Parisian designers' creations, particularly in Paul Poiret's, who renewed the classical female dress, drawing forms after the sinuous aspect of flowers and plants. We must note that this aspect of Parisian fashion during the late nineteenth century is analogous to the painting of the Impressionists. They were also dedicated, in their works painted *en plein air*, to immortalizing pieces of everyday life in its unrepeatability, giving it the duration of an eternal instant. In this way, the fragility of the present, destined to dematerialize at any moment, would be transformed into its internal strength, since the artist was capable of fixing on the canvas all the palpitating power expressed by the labile fragments of existence, preserving its fleeting energy and eternalizing it in the supreme regions of Art. To achieve this result, it was necessary to learn by observing nature carefully, to the point of grasping the secret of its beauty. A beauty that was found mainly in landscapes, observed without filters, and in their immediate power of seduction.

Poiret, the favourite couturier of Boldini's 'vestals', used to send the students of his atelier to the suburban countryside on the outskirts of Paris to draw plants, flowers, trees, and natural landscapes. Their drawings, executed *en plein air*, entered the Maison's decorative repertoire. Dior would follow Poiret in his passion for botany and would decorate his dresses with floral trimmings, among which the image of the rose stands out. The rose is also strongly present in the decoration of those dresses worn by Boldini's models. The rose is in fact the flower which, in its delicate splendour, as a symbol of beauty and fragility embodies the Romantic and Decadent taste par excellence, and often appears as an adornment to decorate both Dior's models and the dresses worn by Boldini's *reines siderales*, frequently conceived as solitary and unattainable divinities: "D'un air de reine qui s'ennuie au milieu de sa cour à genoux, superbe et distraite" (Gautier, 1872: 108). Besides, the identification between woman and flower is typical of the Decadent taste and connotes the Liberty style, which is also called "floral style" due to the sinuous forms

taken from those of plants, particularly the most exotic that have strange shapes and vivid colors, resembling the Boldinian women's languid and delicate silhouettes. This connection between flowers and exquisite and luxurious beauties was established by Walter Pater in one of his first essays, about *Aesthetic Poetry*, written in 1868: "Here, under this strange complex of conditions, as in some medicated air, exotic flowers of sentiment expand, among people of a remote and unaccustomed beauty, somnambulistic, frail, androgynous, the light almost shining through them" (Pater, [1868] 1889: 217). The figure of the femme fatale as a flower with a seductive, voluptuous and corrupt vitality, which is the basis of Boldini's imagination of the modern woman, characterizes both the artistic current of Liberty and contemporary literature, starting from the late Romanticism of Emile Zola, who had a profound influence on Huysmans and the other Decadents:

"But what, at every turn of the avenue, the eye was struck by a large Chinese Hibiscus. The large purple flowers of this species of gigantic mallow live for only a few hours. One would have thought they were the sensual mouths of women opening, the lips red, soft and moist of some giant Messalina, torn apart by kisses, and which were always reborn with their greedy and bloody smile" (Zola, [1872] 2014: 44).

The influence of *fin-de-siècle* Parisian fashion interpreted by Boldini can therefore be found in the alluring gestures of Christian Dior's models, in the chromatic choices and shapes of his clothes and in the materials used to decorate them. These elements characterize a dress of light lilac chiffon adorned with silk prints, dated 1953, which has the identical nuances of the dress worn by Miss Johnston in the portrait Boldini painted in 1906: a dress in satin and chiffon with delicate taffeta embroidery. Boldini, "devotee who officiates at the altars of the emblazoned beauties" (Praz, 1952: 386), as both Christian Dior and Yves Saint Laurent would later do, imagined his women in a transfiguring aura of aesthetic sublimation, just like Marcel Proust, who transformed them into floating marine divinities or imperturbable mythological birds. In this passage, which describes Oriane de Guermantes, Proust seems to visualize a dress from the Autumn/Winter 2005-2006 collection created by John Galliano for Dior, comparable to two Boldinian

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portraits where the illustrious figures wear similar feathered hats and a precious Cartier choker:

“The Duchess wore a simple aigrette in her hair which, dominating her slightly arched nose and protruding eyes, had the look of a feather on a bird’s head. Her neck and shoulders emerged from a snowy billow of muslin against which she would beat a fan of swan feathers; but beneath her, her dress – whose corset had as its only ornament a state of sequins of both metal and of diamonds – modelled her body with precise, exquisite neatness” (Proust, [1920] 1994: 47).

Boldini’s women, with their power of seduction, not only bear witness to an era, but reveal the new psychology – and the new fantasies – this new era brings with it. In the vibrant rhythm of the line, which dynamically caresses the model’s supple forms, is expressed a licentious grace which defines a hitherto unexpressed aspect of femininity, which can become bold and provocative, original and androgynous. Women then become a symbol of the radical change traditional values underwent during the Belle Époque, stimulating the artist to express the capricious and restless side of modern temperaments. Let us remember what D’Annunzio said about the beautiful princess Francesca Massimo d’Arsoli, connecting her charm to her incessant interior life: “... this very strange figure of a woman, in which the rapid nervousness of the movements and the agility of the attitudes and the novelty of the clothing have a charm that I cannot define, and a sparkling grace” (D’Annunzio, [1885] 1948: 30).

Immediately recognizable, Boldini’s muses embody women as the founding lemma of modernity, a place in which the most hidden, sentimental, dreamlike, and erotic impulses converge. The painter establishes himself as an authentic creator of language, capable of equating his noblewomen and the models of his ‘adventure in the atelier’ to the symbols of an era, modelling them in frothy and inflorescent silks, or reducing them to an anatomical element and semantic factor, almost abstract: it is the female body that becomes ‘sign’ and ‘drawing’, which is composed of intelligible form and desirable content.

Galliano’s style, like Boldini’s and Proust’s, is rich and ornate, yet precise and chiselled like a precious diamond. Proust, after all, also engages in a struggle with time to stop its flow, and tries to neutralize its effects through memory, allowing him to compose ‘paintings’ in which time has stopped and life returns in all its intensity and richness. This is the formal exercise and stylistic effort made by Galliano in returning, through imagination and culture, to the glories of the Belle Époque in an attempt to recreate a world and a time now lost; an attempt to return to a historical moment in which artistic

expression coincided with the representation of a social privilege and an eccentric and transgressive way of life inspired by unconventional desires.

Boldini develops his art in parallel with the literary debuts of Marcel Proust – *Les Plaisir et les Jours* came out in 1896, preceded by a brilliant activity as a social chronicler –. Like Proust, Boldini took on the role of interpreter of female beauty in the age of the Belle Époque. That kind of beauty was understood as a repository of exquisite passions, perfected in the external form of their precious and dynamic silhouettes. In these women, who since the 1890s were often portrayed by Boldini in full length, we see a reflection of the exhausted atmosphere of European Decadentism. The artist's secret is the mobility of his brushstroke and the enamelled brilliance of his colours, which give voice to a world subject to whirlwind transformation. This creates multiple facets of a glittering and constantly expanding reality made unfathomable by the horizons opened up by the new symbolist climate.

Let us consider a Galliano dress for the Dior Autumn/Winter 2005-2006 collection,² compared to a Boldini portrait, the *Divine in Blue* (fig. 2), which strongly resembles it, and let us think again about Proust, who saw in the toilettes of the Princesses of Guermantes the “snowy and iridescent materialization of their interior activity” (Proust, [1920] 1994: 51). It is significant that D’Annunzio had used the same words to illustrate the charm of the Italian noblewoman Countess De Angelis, saying that she was “softly snowy” when “she smiled assiduously from that fresh mouth that is like a succulent fruit” (D’Annunzio, [1885] 1948: 12).

In this fashion show in which the designer mixes quotes from the dazzling universe of the Belle Époque and the shady, twilight world of the Edwardian age, we breathe an air full of exquisite scents, so saturated with precious elements that it becomes the backdrop for a sumptuous arabesque, to the point of drawing on the thresholds of the symbol, transforming itself into a reflection – we would always say quoting Proust – of “complicated and flowery cabal” (Proust, [1927] 2012: 192), which arises, like a mysterious herald, from a magical feeling of life.

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² <https://www.gettyimages.es/detail/fotograf%C3%ADa-de-noticias/erin-oconnor-walks-the-runway-during-the-fotograf%C3%ADa-de-noticias/2152868723>.

Figure 2 | Giovanni Boldini, *The Divine in Blue*, watercolor on paper, 1905 ca. Private collection.

Looking at Boldini's paintings and Dior's fashion shows, the models seem to move with the natural elegance that Proust attributed to the Duchess of Guermantes:

"... in the mythological oblivion of her native grandeur, she checked that her veil was well tightened, he smoothed out the folds of his sleeves, he adjusted his cloak, just as the divine swan performs all the movements of its animal species, forgetting that he is a god" (Proust, [1920] 1994: 23).

Boldini's women, like Galliano's, stride in the foamy and light sea of chiffon fabrics decorated with appliques and organza ruffles, hovering as light and fragrant feathers. Tender flowering corollas in graceful shapes expand in space and contain within themselves not only the movement that led them to that miraculous degree of balance, but also, potentially, the development of the gesture in which they are fixed by the painter, communicating the same dynamism of the poses that Dior's models take on the catwalk. And even in this case, Proust's words come to mind, an authentic ecphrasis of the dreamy images hovering before our eyes, in which beauty is not only inscribed in the line of their silhouette, but departs from it, evoking in an "inevitable" way that "complex of invisible lines that the eye cannot refrain from prolonging ideally, miraculous, generated around the woman like an ideal spectrum" (Proust, [1920] 1994: 35).

This can be observed by comparing the portrait of *Countess Speranza* (1899) with many dresses designed by Galliano for Dior, where in both cases the elongated and supple shapes of the model are propagated through the formal echo of the cloak that accompanies the dress. Boldini's influence on contemporary fashion is also active in the youngest and most innovative stylists, who in the wake of Galliano aspire to express the values of a way of life inspired by the cult of beauty. This is what Alexis Mabille does, in dedicating his Autumn/Winter 2013-2014 collection to Boldini, with direct quotes from some of his most famous paintings. Mabille reproduces the precise shapes of the clothes, as in the modern interpretation of the portrait *Black Sash* (1905), in which the painter depicted Ava Lister, the elegant and beautiful Baroness Ribblesdale. Let us think about the definition of shapes modelled on that geometric expansion of the dress in the environmental context that we have seen define Boldini's interpretation of the female silhouette in such a peculiar way.

In Boldini's paintings, as in the creations in which Galliano revives the fashion of the Belle Époque, sidereal *femmes-vêtement* are transformed

into psychological corollaries of a collective taste, which the designer offers as talismans of beauty. To do this, the designer also resorts to direct quotation³ from the myth of the Marchesa Casati (fig. 3), Boldinian muse par excellence, in whose deep, oiled eyes, dilated from inhaling cocaine, strange desires and exquisite passions vibrate. The Dior tulle dress with fox fur stole recalls, in its lilac shade, that of the flower that encircles the waist of the Divine Marchioness, who epitomized an entire era. Boldini's noblewomen are depicted in their esprit as lively heralds of modernity, or captured in a hedonistic languor that portrays them in a voluptuously decadent atmosphere. These two connotations animate the work of Dior, Saint Laurent, and Galliano, all committed to recreating the forms of a new hedonism, which retains the main element from the era of Decadentism, that is, the aim – as Gabriele d'Annunzio writes in his novel *Il Piacere* (1889) – of “making one's life as one makes a work of art”. That is the philosophy which, born in the Victorian era with the aestheticism of Walter Pater and Oscar Wilde, is updated by intensely aestheticizing values in Galliano's dresses (fig. 4).⁴

In a world in which the dominant values are those of a fashion culture made up of the crude display of increasingly cumbersome brands and logos to the detriment of the intrinsic value of the garment, Galliano's choice to immerse the spectator in the aesthetic and spiritual climate of the Belle Époque has the flavour of an explicit distancing from the massification of taste, returning to forcefully affirm, through the suggestions of the sophisticated, cryptic and allegorical world of high fashion, the instances of what Oscar Wilde, in the wake of Pater, called a 'New Hedonism'. In this voluptuous atmosphere, to conclude, we are reminded of the beginning of the Dior fashion show for the 2005-2006 Autumn/Winter collection, where the *Divine in Blue* by Galliano, who inaugurates the show, arrives on a two-horse coupé⁵ staring from the

³ <https://www.gettyimages.es/detail/fotograf%C3%ADa-de-noticias/model-on-the-catwalk-at-the-christian-dior-fotograf%C3%ADa-de-noticias/536022254>.

⁴ https://www.1stdibs.com/it/moda/abbigliamento/abiti-da-sera-e-da-cerimonia/john-galliano-abito-da-sera-a-maniche-lunghe-in-pizzo-nero-e-pelle-formata-fw-2001/id-v_11173672/?modal=intlWelcomeModal.

⁵ <https://www.gettyimages.es/detail/fotograf%C3%ADa-de-noticias/erin-oconnor-walks-the-runway-during-the-fotograf%C3%ADa-de-noticias/2152868974>.

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Figure 3 | Giovanni Boldini, *Marchioness Luisa Casati-Stampa di Soncino*, oil on canvas, 1911. Private collection.

window of the carriage and evoking an image of D'Annunzio's *Sentimental Rome*, the literary equivalent of Boldini's painting:

“Have you noticed the impression that the rapid passage of a carriage gives to those walking on the pavement, alone, at night? Through the glass you can see a female figure and the dazzling whiteness of a fur coat, the glitter of a precious stone, sometimes a precise profile, a bare shoulder where the cloak has fallen, a beautiful neck surrounded by pearls or emeralds. All the ladies, on winter nights, glimpsed in the doubtful light of a headlight, in a speeding coupé, appear beautiful and desirable; and awaken images of passion and pleasure” (D'Annunzio, [1883] 1994: 20).

Figure 4 | Giovanni Boldini, *Madame Eugène II Schneider, née Antoinette de Saint-Sauveur*, oil on canvas, 1901. Unknown location.

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